

Dyes and Dyeing: from Tradition to Industry

Version 1

Description

The aim of the interdisciplinary project, which combines the field of humanities and arts with research methods of natural sciences, is to promote public understanding of technology change processes in the dyeing of textiles in Latvia in the 19th century, providing new knowledge about traditional cultural heritage and industrial history. In the research, based on the study of written sources, practical dyeing, and chemical analyses of historical textile samples, new knowledge will be gained about the history of clothing and the introduction of chemical achievements into public use in Latvia in the 19th century.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Internal and external
consolidation of the University
of Latvia

Researchers

Anete Karlson (0009-0004-6192-7085), Jorens Kviesis (0000-0003-4507-2377)

Organizations
Univeristy of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Dyes and Dyeing: from Tradition to Industry](#)

Description:

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Researchers:

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Organizations:

[Univeristy of Latvia](#)

Contact: [Karlsonē Anete \(anete.karlsonē@lu.lv\)](mailto:anete.karlsonē@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#)

Grants: [Internal and external consolidation of the University of Latvia](#)

Project: [Dyes and Dyeing: from Tradition to Industry](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2026-03-01](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Results of dyeing experiments: *Potentilla erecta* (L.) Raeusch.

The aim of the practical dyeing experiments was to determine what color tones could be obtained from *Potentilla erecta* using different dyeing methods and mordants.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The aim of the practical dyeing experiments was to determine what color tones could be obtained using different dyeing methods and mordants.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

500

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The practical dyeing experiments conducted provide unique visual evidence not documented elsewhere.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

To researchers, artists, students, designers, handcrafters and others

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

Latin names of plants (dyestuffs)

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

ZENODO

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Latin names of plants

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-06-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Anete Karlson (0009-0004-6192-7085)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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